

ISic3387

Funerary inscription for Nikasis, son of Aristokrates

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

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Autopsy

2013.10.04

Last Change

2020-03-05 - Jonathan Prag updated bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Unknown

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 104851

Physical Description

A slightly tapering rectangular block of yellow grey limestone: height 440 mm (the front face is preserved to a maximum height of 435 mm); width 305 mm at the top, 320 mm at the base (measured across the front); depth 275 mm. All four faces are finished, although the left face is somewhat less well finished than the others. The base is rough and unfinished; the top has a roughly worked surface set back from the edge on all four sides, which implies either that a continuation of the stone was subsequently removed from the upper part of the block, or that another stone was previously attached to the top of the block. A painted red band, 85 mm high and slightly proud of the surface, begins some 40 mm below the top of the stone and runs horizontally across the front and right faces of the stone (but there is no trace of this on the rear or left sides). On the front face, below the red band, there is a very lightly recessed field, 205 mm high. This field contains two lines of Greek letters in very light relief. The inscribed field is bordered below by a series of uneven horizontal striations, and there is blank space below this to the base of the stone (the lower edge of the front face is damaged and irregular). There is light damage to all the edges of the stone, including a significant chip to the left margin of the front face

and two substantial gouges in the upper left of the front face of the stone, extending from the red band into the inscribed field.

Dimensions

Height 44 cm

Width 32 cm

Depth 27.5 cm

Layout

Two lines of Greek letters in very light relief, centred in a slightly recessed field in the middle of the front face.

Execution

Relief

letters

Letter Forms

The letters of line 1 are widely spaced. The letters of line 2 are much more tightly

spaced. The letters preserve traces of paint, and appear to have been painted

alternately blue and red. The letters are extremely neatly carved, regular, elegant

and thin, in a light but full relief (on which see below).

Letter forms of note

include the kappa (arms are symmetrical and do not extend to the top and bottom of

the line); alpha (very broad and straight); sigma (consistently formed with open

upper and lower bars); omicron (smaller than the other letters and mid-line);

epsilon (shorter middle-bar).

Letter heights:

Line 1: 35 mm

Line 2: 32-33 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. [N] κκασίς Ἀριστοκρατέος

Apparatus

The lower portion of a vertical stroke can be made out before the kappa, but nothing

more.

Translation (en)

Nikasis, son of Aristokrates

Commentary

In addition to the damage to the upper left edge of the inscribed field, it is also clear from line 2 that the left edge of the text is more heavily weathered and therefore fainter (the initial alpha is visible in strongly raking light, but very faint). In line 1, the lower portion of a vertical stroke can be made out before the kappa, but nothing more. The spacing of line 1 makes it effectively certain that two letters are missing before the kappa. The most plausible restoration is Νικασίς [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?namenoaccents=NIKΑΣΙΣ], of which a dozen instances are known, predominantly of the Hellenistic period and including examples from Rhodes and western Greece (which puts it in the broader Sicilian orbit). The form Νικασίς is not attested in Sicily itself, but the more common name Νικασίωv [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?region=sicily;namenoaccents=NIKΑΣΙΩΝ] is well attested in Sicily, with one instance at Adranon, two at Akrai, one at Henna, two at Lipara, and one at Tauromenion. The patronym, Ἀριστοκράτης [http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/igpn_search.cgi?region=sicily;namenoaccents=ΑΡΙΣΤΟΚΡΑΤΗΣ], is extremely common, including ten instances in Sicily.

The use of relief lettering and bichromatic colouring on alternate letters are both extremely rare in classical epigraphy. Attested examples of both features are discussed in detail in Prag 2017. Relief lettering is not otherwise attested in Sicily (except on a couple of examples of engraved river stones), and the clearest parallels can be found in late Hellenistic funerary epigraphy from western Greece (Corcyra, Ambracia, Apollonia, etc.). Bichrome painted letters are also found in a funerary inscription from Lilybaeum (Marsala) - ISic3662 - but are generally very unusual. A number of examples are attested in funerary inscriptions from ancient Lycia.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645658

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W. 2017. Un unpublished funerary inscription with bichrome painted relief lettering from Hellenistic Syracuse (I.Sicily 3387). *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 203: 119-130.

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